

Vanadium. Part IX. Oxo-Vanadium(IV) Complexes of Pyridine Carboxylic Acids

R. L. Dutta and S. Ghosh

The paper describes a number of oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes of pyridine mono-, di- and tri-carboxylic acids. Pyridine 2- carboxylic acid produces (1) $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{Pic})_2]$ blue, (2) $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(\text{Pic})_2]$ (where X=pyridine, aniline, α -picoline etc), green and (3) $[\text{VO}(\text{OH}\cdots\text{H})(\text{Pic})_2]$ light ash-green. The compounds are all paramagnetic (1.6-1.8 B.M.) and very stable to air.

Pyridine 2,6 dicarboxylic acid (Lut H_2) reacts with vanadyl salts to give (1) deep blue $[\text{VO}(\text{Lut})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ H_2O , which undergoes stepwise dehydration, (2) $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{Lut})]$ deep green, which loses water to furnish (3) $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(\text{Lut})]$ navy blue (where X=pyridine, α -picoline, aniline etc). These complexes, too are paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=1.6-1.8$ B.M.) and perfectly stable to air. Spectral measurements in solution are also reported. Similar and other type complexes are reported for chelidamic acid and for pyridine, 2,4,6 tricarboxylic acid.

Pyridine 2,3 dicarboxylic acid (Quin H_2) provides green coloured H_2 $[\text{VO}(\text{Quin})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ and its ammonium salt is also described. With pyridine the salt $(\text{PyH})_2[\text{VO}(\text{Quin})_2(\text{Py})]$ is obtained.

Extensive measurements in solution are reported for all the above systems. Most of the complexes exhibit only two electronic absorption bands in the visible sometimes with shoulders, the third being buried in the low energy tail of the intense charge transfer band originating in the ultraviolet.

Of the metals in the first transition series, vanadium presents a wide range of chemistry. The valences, that the metal exhibits, spans -1 to $+5$. Currently the coordination complexes of the metal ion in different oxidation states are the most investigated arena.¹⁻¹⁰ One reason for the delay in the exposition of the coordination chemistry of vanadium, has certainly been due to a prevailing conception that the metal has a preference to oxygen donor ligands to nitrogen donors.^{11,12} A series of publications revealed, on the contrary, that this is an over simplification of the issue. It was shown with respect to both oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands, namely o-phenanthroline, oxalic acid, acetylaceton, 8-hydroxyquinoline etc. that in the Irving-Williams series of stability constants of bivalent metal

1. Selbin, *Chem. Revs.*, 1965, **65**, 153.
2. Carlin and Walker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 2128.
3. Selbin and Holmes, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 1116.
4. Horner, Tyree and Venczky, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 844.
5. Sathyanarayana and Patel, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 297.
6. Paris, *Chem. Abst.*, 1965, **62**, 6128.
7. Lahiry, "Coordination Complexes of Vanadium", Ph. D. thesis, Jadavpur University, 1962.
8. (a) Bridgland, Fowles and Walton, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 383.
(b) Ramaiah and Martin, *ibid.*, 1965, **27**, 1663.
9. Pal and Kumar, *ibid.*, 1965, **27**, 2537.
10. (a) Dutta and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1966, **28**,
(b) Dutta, Shyamal and Ghosh, unpublished studies.
11. Martell and Calvin, *Metal Chelate Compounds*", Chapter, Prentice Hall.
12. Sidgwick, "Chemical Elements and their Compounds", Vol.I, Oxford University Press.

cations, the compound-metal ion VO^{2+} has a position higher than copper (II) ion¹³⁻¹⁴. These important results initiated a series of sustained researches in this laboratory on the syntheses and characterisation of vanadium complexes of a host of very unusual coordinating ligands, studying in particular the oxo-vanadium (IV) chemistry. The ligands, on which reports had earlier appeared in this series covered quinaldinic acid¹⁷, benzo-hydroxamic acid and eleven other substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids¹⁸, 3 hydroxyl 1,3-diphenyl triazole and a number of other hydroxytriazenes¹⁹, guanylalkylureas²⁰, benzimidazoles and related ligands²¹.

Our results with quinoline-2- carboxylic acid¹⁷, being highly interesting, we have undertaken a comprehensive programme on the oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes of pyridine-, quinoline-, isoquinoline- and pyrazine carboxylic acids.²² The results of these studies completed over the years will form the subject matter of this and several other forthcoming publications. Besides, we will also have occasions to report some complexes with oxalic acid and iminodiacetic acid. A further study on the vanadium (V) complexes of several other substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids will also be reported at a later stage in this series.

We now set about describing the results of our studies with pyridine carboxylic acids. Such pyridine carboxylic acids were chosen as to form a five membered or a six membered ring around the metal ion. The studies, of necessity, were somewhat limited because of non-availability of some of the methyl pyridines. However, we believe the following few pyridine mono-, pyridine-di- and pyridine-tri carboxylic acids are fairly representative of the broad family of the pyridine carboxylic acids. For brevity, we will often use some abbreviations, which might be regarded as trivial.

Picolinic Acid

Nicotinic Acid

Quinolinic Acid

Lutidinic Acid

Chelidamic Acid

Collidinic Acid

13. Trujilo and Brito, *Chem. Abst.*, 1956, 50, 16528 d.

14. Trujilo, Torres and Brito, *Chem. Abst.*, 1957, 51, 11907.

15. Trujilo and Brito, *Chem. Abst.*, 1960, 54, 2076.

16. Selwood, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience, New York, p.78, 1956.

17. Dutta and Lahiry, *this Journal*, 1961, 30, 1001.

18. Dutta and Lahiry, *ibid.*, 1962, 33, 860; 1963, 40, 53.

19. Dutta and Lahiry, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 67, 857.

20. Dutta and Lahiry, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 863.

21. Dutta and Lahiry, *ibid.*, 1964, 41, 62.

22. A preliminary notice covering some of the syntheses has appeared, Dutta, Ghosh and Lahiry (in part), *Science @ Calcutta*, 1964.

Pyridine 2-carboxylic acid (picolinic acid, Pic H) has the same spatial disposition of the heterocyclic nitrogen and the carboxylic acid as obtained in quinaldinic acid with the only difference that it possesses a smaller weighing factor. Picolinic acid reacts with oxo-vanadium (IV) sulphate to provide a deep skyblue coloured solution around pH 3. This solution on digesting on a steam bath for sometime slowly starts depositing skyblue coloured crystals, which develops into a crust with time. This conforms to a composition $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{Pic})_2]$, losing water on prolonged heating at $160-165^\circ \text{C}$. giving dirty green coloured anhydro compound $[\text{VO}(\text{Pic})_2]$. The complex is a non electrolyte, as shown by its very sparing solubility. Its insolubility in a non-coordinating solvent prevented any attempt towards evaluation of the molecular size. The complex provides a paramagnetic moment of 1.77 B.M. indicating the presence of the one unpaired electron and hence of the quadrivalence of vanadium in the complex. The infrared spectra reveals a strong vanadyl stretching frequency at 962 cm^{-1} and also bands at 850 cm^{-1} and 782 cm^{-1} which might be taken as suggestive of the presence of a coordinated aqua molecule. Just as in the case of quinaldinic acid and some other oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes, the coordinated water may be replaced by other coordinating donor solvents. A series of crystalline complexes of the type $[\text{VO}_2\text{X}(\text{Pic})_2]$, (where X—pyridine, α -picoline, aniline, dimethyl formamide or dimethylaniline) have been characterised. These all possess a strong vanadyl band around 960 cm^{-1} and furnish paramagnetic moments around 1.8 B.M.

While studying the electronic absorption spectra of oxo-vanadium (IV)—picolinic acid system, we observed that the skyblue colour around pH 3 gradually changes to a green around pH 6. (Fig 1). In order to ascertain the empirical metal: ligand ratios in

FIG. 1.

VOSO_4 : Picolinic Acid system—pH variation study.

$\text{VO}^{2+} = 0.04M$. Picolinic Acid = $4 \times 0.04M$.

A pH=3 B pH=4

C pH=6

these two differently coloured systems, we made molar ratio variation at two different pH and at several wave lengths. Both the blue coloured species as well as the light green

species were found to respond to the same metal: ligand ratio, namely 1:2. (Figs 2 & 3). This was indicative of the fact that at somewhat higher pH the coordination zone might be having a form of OH group, resulting from the release of a proton from the water molecules. Operating in a concentrated solution we did succeed in isolating a pale ashgreen compound which analysed like the skyblue product. Assuming that the complex has the configuration $H [VO(OH)(Pic)_2]$, it is expected to show a strong acid reaction and a high conductance value. However, the results indicate that it is better represented as $[VO(OH \cdots H)(Pic)_2]$ with the hydrogen rather more loosely bound than in the skyblue product, though not as loosely as to indicate the formula $H [VO(OH)(Pic)_2]$. The complex readily changes to the skyblue species on the addition of dilute acid. Unlike the skyblue product, this was more soluble in water and could as well be used to furnish the dark green products, $[VO(X)(Pic)_2]$. The IR spectra of $[VO(OH \cdots H)(Pic)_2]$ will be reported in a separate communication.

FIG. 2. $VOSO_4$: Picolinic Acid system.

Molar ratio variation at $pH=9$

$VO^{2+}=0.04M$.

A at $=740 m\mu$.

B at $=550 m\mu$.

FIG. 3. $VOSO_4$: Picolinic Acid system.

Molar ratio variation at $pH=6$.

$VO^{2+}=0.04M$.

A at $=740 m\mu$.

B at $=550 m\mu$.

Pyridine-3-carboxylic acid (nicotinic acid, NicH) also gives rise to an oxo-vanadium (IV) complex of the type $[VO(H_2O)(Nic)_2] \cdot H_2O$ of a light grey-colour. This, too, is paramagnetic but is certainly less stable to the influence of other basic donors. It has not been possible to prepare in pure state compounds of the type $[VO(X)(Nic)_2]$. The absorption spectra of the vanadyl nicotinate in acid medium has been recorded, with the usual bands present. Because of the ready precipitation of the aquo complex in presence of excess reagent, it has not been found possible to check as to what happens with this ligand in the near neutral or in the slightly alkaline range.

Of the many dicarboxylic acids possible, we had access to only three of them, pyridine 2,6-dicarboxylic acid (Lutidinic acid, Lut H_2), 4-hydroxy-pyridine 2,6-dicarboxylic acid (Chelidamic acid, Chel H_2) and pyridine 2,3-dicarboxylic acid (quinolinic acid, quin H_2).

Among these all, lutidinic acid has produced the largest array of vanadyl complexes. Lutidinic acid and vanadyl ion on mixing together under optimum conditions, results in a dark green solution from which deepblue glistening needles can be isolated. The compound analyses as $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Lut})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. This complex undergoes interesting step-

wise dehydration, thus heating around $60\text{-}65^\circ\text{C}$ or leaving it over CaCl_2 in hot summer days or even on long storing, the blue crystals fall to a bright green crystal $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Lut})]$. The blue crystals on heating at 160° provides glistening black crystals, losing all water, $[\text{VO}(\text{Lut})]$. This black compounds when fed in a stoppered bottle with a minute amount of steam first turns violet and then green and finally blue. It has not been possible to find a temperature zone where this stage could be arrested. We believe that the violet stage is the monoquo complex. The production of the black compound from the blue one and its reconversion to the original blue variety through the two intermediate stages may be visualised as a reversible dehydration and rehydration cycle which may be pictured as follows :

Magnetic measurements on the blue, green and the black product prove the existence of one unpaired electron all through. The blue complex is slightly soluble in water and gives a faintly acidic reaction to begin with. However on standing the acidity increases with time and finally reaches a steady value. This is also corroborated by a similar increase in the value of the conductance over the hours. This result probably suggests

the following reaction, which is facilitated in dilute solution and comparatively higher pH .

TABLE I

Conductance measurements $(\lambda_{\infty}$ in $Ohm^{-1} Cm^2 Mole^{-1}$)

Complex	Dilution (in litres)	128	256	512	1024
$[VO (H_2O)_2 (Collid H)]H_2O$ or $H[VO (H_2O)_2 (Collid H) H_2O]$	λ_{∞}	222.8	285.1	374.1	496.6
λ_{∞} (mean) = 357.1	λ_{∞}	236.4	297.4	387.7	507.1
$H_2[VO (Quin)_2 H_2O]$	λ_{∞}	118.2	134.8	152.1	169.8
λ_{∞} (mean) = 149.5	λ_{∞}	125.4	140.7	157.6	173.4
$(NH_4)_2 [VO (Quin)H_2O] 3H_2O$	λ_{∞}	129.8	144.9	158.1	161.2
λ_{∞} (mean) = 154.7	λ_{∞}	137.8	151.1	163.9	164.6

*was calculated with the help of Wolden's relation $\lambda_{\infty} = \lambda_{\infty} (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times V^{\frac{1}{2}})$

where n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions.

TABLE II

pH measurements

Complex	Concentration	pH (after attainment of equilibrium)
$[VO (Lut) (H_2O)_2]H_2O$	0.002M	4.35* (after 26 hours)
$[VO (Collid H) (H_2O)_2] H_2O$	0.01M	2.46
$H_2[VO (Quin)_2 (H_2O)]$	0.005M	2.36
$[VO (Pic)_2 (H_2O)(OH)]$	0.01M	6.20

*The starting pH (after 15 minutes of solution making) was = 5.50

This is reminiscent of the way picolinic acid has been found to react. The composition of the complex is such that the ligand behaves as tridentate. This, certainly is permitted and indeed, favoured by the stereochemical and valence requirements of the central metal atom. This, however, is not always the case with this particular ligand. The bipoisitive silver complex²³ of this ligand $[Ag (Lut H)_2]$ is an example in point, where in it has been shown that in order to attain the square planer configuration one—COOH of each of the ligand molecules remains free and the ligand behaves as bidentate. As against this, reference may be made to a peroxocomplex of vanadium(V), where the ligand functions as a tridentate one.²⁴ A magnetic moment value of 1.69 B.M. is what one expects for such a complex. A strong infrared band at $980 cm^{-1}$ is also characteristic of a metal—oxygen double bond. We then set about replacing the aqua molecules by other donor centres such as pyridine, picolines, aniline etc. The general reaction with the above donor bases lead to

23. Banerjee and Ray, *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 207.

24. Hartkamp, *Angew. Chem.*, 1939, 71, 553.

complexes of the type $[\text{VO}(\text{Lut})(\text{X})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (where X-pyridine etc). Despite our using an excess of the amine or the heterocyclic bases, we failed to obtain any other higher base substituted complex, although one other bidentate ligand, such as O-phenanthroline or dipyridyl could be easily introduced. This is presumably due to a stronger basic surroundings, which inhibits such formation of a dipyridine complex. The ease with which a bidentate ligand goes in, even at a temperature of $0-5^\circ\text{C}$, indicates the cis disposition of the aqua molecules. In this light the formation of a mono tetrahydrofuran or monodioxan complex is again revealing. There is probably not much difference in these oxygen donors so as to initiate total substitution of the aqua molecules by either tetrahydrofuran or dioxan. The above complexes in general have a green colour. The pyridine complex on strong heating loses the water molecules inside and outside the coordination zone and produces an intense navy blue coloured complex $[\text{VO}(\text{Py})(\text{Lut})]$, which retains the pyridine very tenaciously. This navy blue complex slowly reverts to the original green one on keeping in contact with water and may be represented as follows:

The corresponding α -Picoline compound behaves similarly. We will shortly present some thermal decomposition results, which will say more of these complexes. These complexes are also non-electrolytes and offer normal magnetic moments (1.6—1.8 B.M.)

TABLE III

Magnetic Measurements

Complex	$\text{Dia}^{16}(\text{Corr.}) \times 10^6$	$\lambda_M(\text{Corr.}) \times 10^6$	* μ_{eff} (B.M.)
Aquo-bis-Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV). $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$	130.80	1272.80	1.77
Pyridine-bis Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]$	167.36	1467.36	1.89
Aniline-bis Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$	181.56	1420.56	1.87
α -Picoline-bis Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$	180.62	1412.62	1.86
Dimethylaniline-bis Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N})]$	205.28	1414.88	1.85
Bis-Nicotinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) hydrate $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	148.5	1321.9	1.80
Diaquo-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) trihydrate $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_3\text{NO}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$	106.61	1164.81	1.69
Diaquo-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_3\text{NO}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	93.91	1219	1.73
Aquo-Pyridine-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium IV monohydrate $\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_3\text{NO}_4)_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	130.47	1152	1.68

TABLE III (contd.)

Complex	$\text{Dia}^{16} (\text{Corr}) \times 10^6$	$\lambda (\text{Corr.}) \times 10^6$	$\mu_{\text{eff}} (\text{B.M.})$
Pyridine-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium IV [VO (C ₇ H ₅ NO ₄) (C ₅ H ₅ N)]	117.77	1149.77	1.68
Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) [VO (C ₇ H ₅ NO ₄)]	68.51	1197.91	1.70
Aquo- α -Picolin. Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium IV [VO (C ₇ H ₅ NO ₄) (C ₆ H ₇ N) (H ₂ O)]	143.78	1241.99	1.75
Aniline-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium IV [VO (C ₇ H ₅ N O ₄) (C ₆ H ₇ N)]	191.97	1210.97	1.73
Dimethylaniline-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium IV [VO (C ₇ H ₅ NO ₄) (C ₈ H ₁₁ N)]	155.69	1230.09	1.75
Tetrahydrofuran-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium IV monohydrate (VO (C ₇ H ₅ NO ₄) (C ₄ H ₈ O)) (H ₂ O)	120.56	1176.76	1.70
Pyridine-Chelidamato oxo-Vanadium IV monohydrate [VO (C ₇ H ₅ NO ₃) (C ₅ H ₅ N)] (H ₂ O)	135.99	1198.59	1.72
Aniline-Chelidamato oxo-Vanadium IV [VO (C ₇ H ₅ NO ₃) (C ₆ H ₇ N)]	137.49	1198	1.72
Aquo- α -Picoline-Chelidamato oxo-Vanadium IV [VO (C ₇ H ₅ NO ₃) (C ₆ H ₇ N) (H ₂ O)]	149.25	1229.95	1.74
Diaquo-Collidinato oxo-Vanadium IV monohydrate [VO (C ₈ H ₃ NO ₆) (H ₂ O) ₂]H ₂ O	121.93	1234.03	1.75
Anilinium salt of aniline oxo-collidinato oxo-Vanadium IV. (C ₆ H ₇ NH) [VO (C ₈ H ₃ NO ₆) (C ₆ H ₇ N)]	210.75	1276.99	1.77
α -Picolinium salt of α -Picoline-oxo collidinato oxo-Vanadium IV. (C ₆ H ₇ NH) [VO (C ₈ H ₃ NO ₆) (C ₆ H ₇ N)]	208.87	1266.15	1.76
Pyridinium salt of Pyridine collidinato oxo-Vanadium IV. (C ₅ H ₅ NH) [VO (C ₈ H ₃ NO ₆) (C ₅ H ₅ N)]	195.05	1275.93	1.77

* μ_{eff} (in Bohr Magnetron) was calculated with the help of the relation $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 \sqrt{\lambda_{\text{M}} (\text{corr.}) T}$ B.M. where T = absolute temperature. The instrument used for the measurement of magnetic susceptibility was a Gouy Balance and G.R. Copper sulphate pentahydrate (E. Merck) was used as the calibrant.

Absorption spectral studies at different pH values show the existence of another dirty green coloured species at higher pH. Molar variation at the lower pH (pH 3) indicates a maximum at 1:1 metal ligand ratio, whereas a similar measurements at the higher pH gives a value of 1:2 metal ligand ratio. (Figs. 4 & 5). We have not been successful in isolating this species in a reasonably pure state. However, it is easily appreciated that the second lutidinic acid molecule displaces the two aqua molecules and functions as a bidentate, leaving the second COOH free and uncoordinated. In view of the paucity of examples of seven coordination in oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes, such a configuration appears reasonable.

Chelidamic acid, Chel H₄ (4-hydroxy pyridine 2,6 dicarboxylic acid) presented a good deal of difficulties during the synthetic works because of its insolubility in most solvents. Repeated attempts to prepare the chelidamic acid analogue of the blue

$[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Lut})]\text{H}_2\text{O}$ failed. However, a few complexes of the type $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{Chel})]$ (where X: pyridine or α -picoline) were obtained. On strong heating the pyridine complex lost the complex bound water with a colour change from olive green to a lighter shade. Because of the insolubility of the reagent we did not consider worthwhile undertaking any absorption spectral studies in solution.

FIG. 4. VOSO_4 : Lutidinic Acid system.

Molar ratio variation at $\text{pH}=6.2$

$\text{VO}^{+2}=0.04M$.

A at $=740 \text{ m}\mu$.

B at $=620 \text{ m}\mu$.

The other dicarboxylic acid that we have studied namely, pyridine 2,3 dicarboxylic acid (quinolinic acid Quin H_2) cannot possibly function as a tridentate. Thus by the reaction of vanadium(IV) hydroxide and quinolinic acid, a deep green complex has been isolated. Analysis indicates two ligand groups per vanadium, possibly $\text{H}_2[\text{VO}(\text{Quin})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. The ammonium salt has also been characterised. The ammonium salt registers a rather high molar conductance value, due primarily to a high prevailing temperature. The corresponding value of the free acid is reasonable which indicates the complex is dissociated to an appreciable extent. The aqueous solution of the complex acid ($0.005 M$) registers a pH value of 2.36 and a molar conductance value (339.6 mhos) are good evidence towards a strong acid character of the complex (Tables I & 2). A rigorous pH titration of the complex acid against a standard base in order to evaluate the pK and pK_2 values, was not, however, undertaken because of the ready susceptibility of the complex on treatment with alkalis. The pyridinium salt has also been prepared, which shows a coordinated pyridine as also two other pyridines, evidently present as pyridinium cations. The equivalent weights of these two complexes have been determined by an ion-exchange technique and have been found to agree well with other analytical results. (Table VI).

Pyridine 2,4,6 tricarboxylic acid (Collidinic acid, Collid H_3) functions as a tridentate with the 4-COOH remaining free and uncoordinated. The complex $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Collid H})]\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been obtained in the form of shining greenish blue crystals in rather low yield. The free COOH gets neutralised, when the complex is treated with a base such as pyridine, furnishing $\text{PyH}[\text{VO}(\text{Py})(\text{Collid})]$. The magnetic moments of all these complexes are normal and come within the range 1.6 -1.8 B.M., typical of a $3d^1$ vanadium (IV) ion.

Absorption Spectra of the oxo-vanadium (IV) Complexes.—Recently tremendous enthusiasm has been shown in the spectral interpretation of the oxo-vanadium(IV) complexes. In general, oxo-vanadium(IV) complexes exhibit three low intensity bands in the 10,000-30,000 cm^{-1} region, following the bands in oxo-penta aquo vanadium (IV) ion²⁵. Since

the introduction of these ideas many workers have interpreted the spectra of their complexes on this model²³ often band III usually a shoulder, is buried under the low energy tail of the highly intense charge transfer band lying in the ultraviolet region. Another "cluster band" scheme has also been proposed wherein a total of four d-d transitions are expected within the same energy range. Indeed resolution of the absorption bands in bis acetylacetonato oxo-vanadium (IV) at low temperature and the appearance of four did transitions in oxo-vanadium (IV) tartrate, -lactate, -malate and mandelate have been observed adding weight to such a scheme of level splitting.^{25,26}

TABLE IV
Electronic Absorption Spectral Data

Complex	State	Band II			Band I		
		$\lambda_{\max}$ ($m\mu$)	wave no. (cm^{-1})	ϵ	$\lambda_{\max}$ $m\mu$	wave no. (cm^{-1})	ϵ
1. $[VO(H_2O)_2(Lut)]H_2O$	(in aq. solution)				(740sh)*	13500	19.0
		650	15400	16.0	840	11900	26.9
2. $[VO(H_2O)(Py)(Lut)]$	(in alcoholic solution)				(700sh)*	(14300)	24.8
		600	16700	24.0	800	12500	28.0
3. $[VO(H_2O)_2(Colloid H)]H_2O$	(in aq. solution)	680	14700	30.4	840	11900	24.0
4. $(NH_4)_2[VO(Quin)_2H_2O]$ 3H ₂ O	,, ,,	560	17800	12.6	740	13500	32.0

*may also be regarded as bands.

In view of the above prevailing situation with respect to absorption spectra, we have studied in an extensive manner the absorption spectra of our complexes in solution at room temperature over the wave length region 320 $m\mu$ to 860 $m\mu$ and the results of such measurements are shown in the Tables.

The symmetry in aquo bis picolinato oxo-vanadium (IV) is no higher than C_{2v} and its spectra recorded in presence of excess picolinic acid over the pH range 3 to 6 reveals only two absorption bands, one around 540 $m\mu$ ($18,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the other at 740 $m\mu$ ($13,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) at pH 3 and again at 580 $m\mu$ ($17,800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 745 $m\mu$ ($13,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) at pH 6.0. (Fig. 1). In none of the spectra reported for this system, did we observe a third absorption band around 24,000—29,000 cm^{-1} region, presumably being hidden under an intense charge transfer spectra.

For pyridine 2,6 dicarboxylic acid measurements in solution in presence of excess ligand at pH 3.0 again provides only two bands at 620 $m\mu$ ($16,100\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and at 780 $m\mu$ ($12,800\text{ cm}^{-1}$). At pH 7.0, the colour changes from green to brownish green, empirical metal; ligand ratio changing to 1:2 from 1:1, again two bands are observed at 590 $m\mu$ ($17,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and a shoulder at 670 $m\mu$ ($12,800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) with the suggestion of a third

26. Selbin, Ortolano and Smith, *ibid*, 1963, 2, 1915.

27. Ortolano, Selbin and McGlynn, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, 41, 262.

28. Selbin and Morpergo, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 673.

band existing in the long wave length region beyond 850 $m\mu$. Here to, band III was masked by charge transfer spectra with its origin in the ultraviolet. The complex $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Lut})]\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was also dissolved in water and its spectra recorded, which reveals quite a deal of difference three bands in the visible from that recorded in presence of excess reagent. This is not unreasonable because of pronounced dissociation that we observed from $p\text{H}$ and conductance measurements. The complex $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Collid H})]\text{H}_2\text{O}$ also showed two bands at 680 $m\mu$ ($14,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and at 840 $m\mu$ ($11,900\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The spectra of $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Py})(\text{Lut})]$ was run in alcoholic pyridine and again two prominent absorption bands around 600 $m\mu$ ($16,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and at 800 $m\mu$ ($12,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$), and a less pronounced one at 700 $m\mu$ ($14,300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were observed. The ammonium salt of the quinolinic acid complex also reveals two absorption bands at 560 $m\mu$ ($17,800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and at 740 $m\mu$ ($13,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) (Figs. 6 & 7). Many of the complexes reported in this paper possess low symmetry and we believe reflectance spectral studies, particularly at low temperature, might as well furnish more interesting spectral data than what could be unearthed in the room temperature solution studies. Since we are not equipped with diffuse reflectance spectral measurements, we are unable to elaborate on the spectral characteristics of these complexes any further.

FIG. 5. VOSO_4 : Lutidinic Acid system— $p\text{H}$ variation study.
 $\text{VO}^{+2} = 0.01\text{ M}$, Lutidinic Acid = $3 \times 0.01\text{ M}$.
 A at $p\text{H} = 7.2$ C at $p\text{H} = 5.2$
 B at $p\text{H} = 6.2$ D at $p\text{H} = 4.02$
 E at $p\text{H} = 3.0$

FIG. 6. Absorption spectra of some solid complexes put in solution.
 A. $[\text{VO}(\text{Lut})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.01\text{ M}$ in water
 B. $[\text{VO}(\text{CollidH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.01\text{ M}$ in water
 C. $[\text{VO}(\text{Lut})(\text{Py})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] - 0.005\text{ M}$ in alcohol
 D. $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{VO}(\text{Quin})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.01\text{ M}$ in water.

TABLE V

Electronic Absorption Spectral Measurements (in presence of excess ligands at different $p\text{H}$)

(A) System: Vanadylsulphate Picolinic Acid = 1:4

$p\text{H}$	Band II			Band I		
	λ_{max} $m\mu$	wave no. Cm^{-1}	Molar ϵ	λ_{max} $m\mu$	wave no. Cm^{-1}	molar ϵ
3	545	18350	10.25	740	13500	23.10
6	535	18680	12.97	730	13700	22.37

TABLE V (contd.)

(B) System: Vanadylsulphate: Lutidinic Acid=1:3

pH	Band II			Band I		
	$\lambda_{\max}$ m μ	wave no. cm $^{-1}$	molar ϵ	$\lambda_{\max}$ m μ	wave no. cm $^{-1}$	molar ϵ
3.02	620	16100	9.0	780	12800	5.5
6.2	620	16100	6.42	780	12800	8.75
7.2	555 sh 590	17000	23.9 25.10	670	12800	27.7

TABLE VI

Equivalent weight Determination

Complex	Equivalent Weight	
	Found	Calculated
H ₂ [VO (Quin) ₂ H ₂ O]	219.9	206.5
(NH ₄) ₂ [VO (Quin) ₂ H ₂ O] 3H ₂ O	256.8	252.5

EXPERIMENTAL

Vanadyl Sulphate used in these work was either a pentahydrate of E. Merck or a monohydrate of B. D. H. Chelidamic acid was a product of L. Light. Other pyridine carboxylic acids were prepared by permanganate oxidation of the respective picolines by following standard procedures.

Aquo-bis-Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV)—Picolinic acid (0.3 g) and Vanadyl sulphate pentahydrate (0.25 g) were dissolved in 20 ml and 5 ml hot water and the two solutions were mixed. The pH of this blue solution was gradually raised to a pH 3.5-4.5 by the addition of dilute ammonia when the colour of the solution became green and was kept overnight at room temperature. A crust of blue mass was obtained, filtered, washed with water and rectified spirit and dried over CaCl₂. It was insoluble in alcohol, ether, acetone, benzene, chloroform, carbontetrachloride, dichlorobenzene etc. but soluble in pyridine and picolines forming deep green solutions. Found: V, 14.3; N, 8.4; H₂O (as loss at 160-165°), 5.3. Reqd. for [VO (C₆H₄NO₂)₂ (H₂O)]; V, 14.0; N, 8.14; H₂O, 5.47 percent.

Pyridine-bis-Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV).—The freshly prepared above blue compound was washed repeatedly with water, sucked dry and the compound (0.4 g) was powdered and heated with pyridine (10 ml) on a steam bath under reflux for 1½ hours. The deep green solution was allowed to evaporate under a fan at room temperature when dark green crystals appeared. These were filtered, washed with anhydrous alcohol until free from pyridine and dried over CaCl₂. Found: V, 12.7; N, 11.0. Reqd. for [VO(C₆H₄NO₂)₂(C₄H₅N)]; V, 13.0; N, 10.8 percent.

The compound liberated pyridine on heating with sodiumhydroxide solution.

Aniline-bis-Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV).—The freshly prepared blue compound (0.4 g) was heated with freshly distilled aniline (15 ml) on a steam bath under reflux until a clear violet solution obtained. It was then treated with rectified spirit (25 ml) and further,

refluxed for one hour and allowed to stand at room temperature when a very pale violet crystalline precipitate settled down. This was filtered, washed with rectified spirit until free from aniline and dried over CaCl_2 . The dried compound was almost white with a faint violet tinge. The compound liberated aniline on heating with sodium hydroxide solution. Found: V, 12.82; N, 10.53. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$: V, 12.62; N, 10.40 percent.

< *Picoline-bis-Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV)*.—Picolinic acid (0.3 g) was dissolved by warming in *a*-Picoline (5 ml) and vanadylsulphate (0.25 g) dissolved in minimum water was added to it with stirring and the clear solution was allowed to evaporate under a fan for 8 hours and then kept overnight in a vacuum desiccator. The greenish compound left as residue was washed with icecold water first to remove *a*-Picoline sulphate and then with rectified spirit until free from *a*-Picoline and finally dried over CaCl_2 . The dried compound was of a very lightblue colour and liberated *a*-Picoline when heated with sodium hydroxide solution. Found: V, 12.72; N, 10.31. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N})]$: V, 12.62; N, 10.40 percent.

Dimethylformamide bis-Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV): Same procedure as in the case of the above *a*-Picoline compound was adopted. The dried product was a lightbluish powder which liberated dimethylformamide on heating with caustic soda solution. Found: V, 13.32; N, 10.96. Reqd. for $[(\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{NO}))_2]$: V, 13.28; N, 10.93 percent.

Dimethylaniline-bis-Picolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV)—The procedure followed in this case was exactly same as the one followed for the aniline compound. The dried product is a skyblue powder which liberated aniline when heated with caustic soda. Found: V, 11.71; N, 9.63. Reqd. for $[(\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}))_2]$: V, 11.80; N, 9.72 percent.

Bis-Nicotino oxo-Vanadium (IV) dihydrate—Vanadyl sulphate (0.5 g) was dissolved in water (5 ml) and was added to a solution of nicotinic acid (0.5 g) dissolved in hot rectified spirit (25 ml) and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.4-3.5 when a greyish violet precipitate gradually settled down. It was filtered, washed first with cold water and then with rectified spirit sucked dry and finally dried over CaCl_2 . It is a very light granular solid greyish in colour. Found: V, 14.81; N, 8.02; H_2O (as loss at 105°) 10.52. Reqd. for $[(\text{VO}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{NO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$: V, 14.69; N, 8.07; H_2O , 10.37 percent.

Di-quo-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) monohydrate. (Blue):—Vanadyl sulphate (0.5 g) and lutidinic acid (0.4 g) were dissolved in hot water (20 ml) when a brightgreen solution was obtained. It was then cooled in a refrigerator for 2 hours when the excess reagent precipitated was filtered off and the filtrate kept overnight in a refrigerator. Shining blue crystals were obtained, filtered, washed with rectified spirit and dried in air for 4-5 hours. The compound forms blue needles soluble in hot water but sparingly soluble in cold water and alcohol. Found: V, 18.08; N, 4.64; H_2O (loss at $165\text{-}70^\circ$) 19.07. Reqd. $[(\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_3\text{NO}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O}))_2]$: V, 17.83; N, 4.89; H_2O , 18.88 percent.

Di-quo-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) (Green): The above blue compound was heated in an airoven at $65^\circ\text{-}70^\circ$ for 1 hour when the blue colour changed to lightgreen. It was then kept over CaCl_2 when no further change in colour occurred. Found: V, 18.73; N, 5.22; H_2O (loss at $165^\circ\text{-}70^\circ$) 12.32. Reqd. for $[(\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_3\text{NO}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O}))_2]$: V, 18.90; N, 5.18; H_2O , 12.3 percent.

The same green compound was also obtained when the blue compound was kept over CaCl_2 or conc. H_2SO_4 for 3 days.

Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) (Black): The blue mother compound was heated at $165-170^\circ$ for $1\frac{1}{2}$ to 2 hours when a shining black having apparently the same crystalline form of the blue compound was obtained. It was kept in a desiccator, allowed to cool to room temperature and then analysed. Found: V, 21.91; N, 6.14. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)]$: V, 21.99; N, 6.03 percent.

When minute quantities of steam were gradually fed to the black compound kept in a stoppered bottle a violet coloured substance is first observed which rapidly turned into a green one and finally to the blue mother compound with the feeding of more steam.

Aquo-Pyridine-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) (Bright green):—The blue mother compound (0.5 g) was suspended as powder in a mixture of rectified spirit (5 ml) and pyridine (2 ml) and heated on a steam bath when a brightgreen solution was obtained. The solution was then evaporated nearly to dryness, cooled and excess of rectified spirit was added when a brightgreen crystalline compound was obtained. This was filtered, washed with spirit until free from any smell of pyridine and finally dried over CaCl_2 . The dried product was crystalline and of brightgreen colour. It liberated pyridine on heating with caustic soda solution. Found: V, 14.49; N, 8.11; H_2O (loss at $100-105^\circ$). Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$: V, 14.62; N, 8.02; H_2O 2 percent.

Pyridine-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium IV. (Navyblue): The above green compound was heated at $105^\circ-110^\circ$ in an airoven for 1 hour when the colour changed to navyblue (above 80°) and remains as such. This was cooled over CaCl_2 and analysed. This compound did not change colour on exposure to dry air but gradually turned green in contact with water and that this green compound was the parent green one was proved by analysis. The navyblue compound suffered no loss when heated upto 165° . Found: V, 16.18; N, 8.87. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]$: V, 16.29; N, 8.95 percent.

Aquo- α -Picoline-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) (Green): This compound was obtained as the corresponding green pyridine compound. Found: V, 14.67; N, 8.03; H_2O (loss at 105°) 5.29. Reqd for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$: V, 14.79; N, 8.12; H_2O 5.21 percent.

α -Picoline-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) (Blue): This compound was obtained from the green monohydrate by heating at $85^\circ-90^\circ$ in an airoven. This had a darkblue colour. Found: V, 15.51; N, 8.67. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$: V, 15.60; N, 8.56 percent.

This compound lost α -picoline when heated above 95°C which is evident from the smell of α -Picoline.

Aniline-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV): This was prepared as for pyridine complex using aniline instead of pyridine. The dried product was a darkgreen crystalline compound. Found: V, 15.49; N, 8.44. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$: V, 15.60; N, 8.56 percent. The compound suffered practically no loss at $170^\circ-175^\circ$.

Dimethyl aniline-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV): This compound was obtained as above. The dried product was a dirtygreen granular solid. Found: V, 14.24; N, 7.95. Reqd. for

$[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)] (\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N})$: V, 14.36; N, 7.89 percent. The compound suffered no appreciable loss upto 175° .

Tetrahydrofuran-Lutidinato-oxo-Vanadium (IV). Monohydrate: The blue $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4) (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was refluxed for 3-3½ hours with tetrahydrofuran, filtered, washed with anhydrous alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . The dried product is a green crystalline compound. Found: V, 15.92; N, 4.41. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4) (\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}) \text{H}_2\text{O}]$: V, 15.83; N, 4.32 percent.

This compound began to lose both water as well as tetrahydrofuran above 80° and was ultimately converted into the black compound $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)]$ at 170° . Total loss: Found: 28.17. Reqd: 27.95 percent.

Dioxan-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) monohydrate: This compound was obtained as above and has the same characteristics except that its colour is a shade darker. Found: V, 15.17; N, 4.22. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4) (\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_2) (\text{H}_2\text{O})]$: V, 15.08; N, 4.14 percent.

This compound behaved exactly like the tetrahydrofuran analogue. Total loss: Found: 31.61. Reqd: 31.36 percent.

Benzidine-Lutidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV). The blue mother compound (0.5 g) was powdered and refluxed with benzidine (0.5 g) in alcohol (20 ml) on a steam bath for 2½-3 hours, filtered, washed with alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . The dried product was a dirty green powder. Found: V, 12.11; N, 10.21 percent. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4) (\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2)]$: V, 12.26; N, 10.1 percent. The compound suffered no appreciable loss upto 150° .

Aquo-Pyridine-Chelidamato oxo-Vanadium (IV).—Chelidamic acid (0.4 g) was dissolved in a hot mixture of pyridine (2 ml) and water (5 ml) and gradually added to a solution of Vanadyl sulphate (0.5 g) in hot water (3-4 ml) and filtered. The filtrate on cooling deposited olivegreen granular precipitate which was washed with rectified spirit till free from pyridine and dried over CaCl_2 . It is a granular olivegreen solid and liberated pyridine when heated with caustic soda solution. Found: V, 14.72; N, 7.97; H_2O (loss at 160°), 5.37. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_3) (\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}) (\text{H}_2\text{O})]$: V, 14, 79; N, 8.11; H_2O , 5.2 percent.

Pyridine-Chelidamato oxo-Vanadium (IV).—The above olivegreen compound was heated at 160 - 165° in an airoven for 1-1½ hours when the colour faded slightly. This was cooled in a desiccator and analysed. Found: V, 15.71; N, 8.45. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_3) (\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]$: V, 15.59; N, 8.45 percent.

Aquo- α -Picoline-Chelidamato oxo-Vanadium (IV).—The same procedure as in the case of corresponding pyridine compound was adopted using α -picoline in place of pyridine. The dried product was a green granular solid. Found: V, 14.32; N, 7.61. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_3) (\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}) (\text{H}_2\text{O})]$: V, 14.21; N, 7.80 percent.

This compound on heating above 100° began to lose α -picoline which is completed at 160° . (Found total loss 26.88 percent; loss of one α -picoline along with one water molecule requires 27.02 percent). The final product, after cooling over CaCl_2 was of light ash colour.

Aniline-Chelidamato oxo-Vanadium (IV): Chelidamic acid (0.4 g) was dissolved in a hot mixture of freshly distilled aniline (3 ml) and water (10 ml) which was then gradually

added, with constant stirring, to a solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.5 g) in hot water (5 ml) when a granular green precipitate was thrown down. This was digested on steam bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the almost colourless mother liquor was decanted off. The residue was then heated again with water (10 ml) on steam bath, filtered, washed with rectified spirit till free from aniline and dried over CaCl_2 . The dried product was a dark green granular solid. Found: V, 15.02; N, 8.30. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$: V, 14.96; N, 8.21 percent.

The compound suffered no appreciable loss upto 165-170°.

Diagu-Collidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV) monohydrate (Greenish blue): Vanadyl sulphate (0.5 g) and Collidine acid (0.4 g) were dissolved in hot water (15-20 ml) and the resultant bright green solution was kept overnight in a refrigerator. The excess reagent precipitate was filtered off and the filtrate kept overnight again in a refrigerator when shining greenish blue crystals appeared which were filtered, washed with rectified spirit and dried in air for 3-4 hours. The yield is poor and the dried compound is fairly soluble in hot water and alcohol. Found: V, 15.15; N, 4.11; H_2O (loss at 105-110°) 16.28. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$ H_2O : V, 15.27; N, 4.19; H_2O , 16.16 percent.

Pyridinium salt of pyridine collidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV): The above compound (0.5 g) was heated with pyridine (2-3 ml) on steam bath when a deep green solution was obtained. This was then treated with rectified spirit (20 ml) and warmed on water bath for 1 hour when a brownish green precipitate settled down. This was then cooled in ice, filtered and washed repeatedly with rectified spirit until no smell of pyridine was left and then dried over CaCl_2 . The dried product is a brownish green granular solid. Found: V, 11.17; N, 9.38. Reqd. for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH} [(\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}))]$: V, 11.28; N, 9.51 percent.

α -Picolinium salt of α -Picoline-Collidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV). The procedure for preparation of this compound was the same as for the corresponding pyridine compound using α -picoline in place of pyridine. The colour of the dried product was almost same as that of the pyridine analogue. Found: V, 11.42; N, 9.29. Reqd. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{NH} [\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N})]$: V, 11.39; N, 9.37 percent.

The compound suffered no appreciable loss at 105-110°.

Anilinium salt of Aniline Collidinato oxo-Vanadium (IV): Procedure for preparation same as above. Aniline was used instead of pyridine. The final product is a yellowish green powder. Found: V, 11.27; N, 9.27. Reqd. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{NH} [\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$: V, 11.39; N, 9.37 percent.

O-bis quinolinato-oxo-Vanadium (IV) acid: Vanadyl sulphate (1.5 g) was converted into vanadyl hydroxide with dilute sodium hydroxide and washed free from alkali and sulphate. It was then heated with quinolinic acid (1.0 g) dissolved in hot water (15 ml) when a blue black solution was formed and the excess of Vanadyl hydroxide was removed by filtration. The clear solution (pH 3-3.5) was then evaporated on a steam bath to dryness. The residue was then triturated repeatedly with rectified spirit, filtered, washed with spirit and acetone and dried over CaCl_2 . It is an olive green powder highly soluble in water. Found: V, 12.33; N, 6.83; H_2O (loss at 105°-110°) 4.43. Reqd. for $\text{H}_2[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$: V, 12.29; N, 6.75; H_2O , 4.31 percent.

Ammonium salt of bis quinolinato oxo-Vanadium (IV): The clear blue black solution obtained by dissolving vanadyl hydroxide in quinolinic acid solution and subsequent

filtration was then concentrated to a small volume (8-10 ml), cooled in ice and the pH was raised to approximately 6.5 by adding dilute ammonium hydroxide. Then excess rectified spirit was added to it with vigorous stirring when a granular green precipitate settled down, filtered and washed with spirit. This was then dissolved in minimum water, reprecipitated by adding excess spirit, filtered, washed with spirit and dried over CaCl_2 . The dry product is a dirty green solid, soluble in water turning gummy on exposure to moist air. Found: V, 9.99; N, 11.23; H_2O (loss at 100°), 14.5. Reqd. for $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$: V, 10.14; N, 11.13; H_2O , 14.3 percent.

Pyridinium salt of pyridine bis quinolino oxo-Vanadium (IV) $\text{H}_2[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (0.5 g) was treated with pyridine (2 ml) and rectified spirit (5 ml) when a deepgreen solution was obtained which was then evaporated to dryness. This process was repeated till there was no smell of pyridine. Finally the solid residue was triturated with absolute alcohol, filtered and dried over CaCl_2 for at least 48 hours (otherwise the compound became gummy as soon as it was exposed to air). It is a darkgreen crystalline solid soluble in water. Found: V, 7.91; N, 11.20. Reqd. for $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH})_2[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_4)_2 \cdot (\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]$: V, 8.02; N, 11.09 percent.

GENERAL EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Vanadium was estimated as V_2O_5 after igniting the complex. Nitrogen was estimated by semi micro Dumas technique.

Equivalent weight was determined by running the aqueous solutions of the complex species through an anion exchanger (IR, 400 A Cl^- form) and finally estimating the liberated acid. The equivalent weight was given by:

$$\text{E. W.} = \frac{W \times 36.5}{V \times S \times 0.001825}$$

where W = Weight of the complex taken.

V = Volume of alkali required for titration.

S = Strength of alkali used.

0.001825 = weight in gms of HCl in 1 ml $N/20$ HCl

36.5 = Molecular weight of HCl.

Absorption spectra was recorded in a Uvispek spectrophotometer using 1 cm cell and conductance by a Phillips conducting Bridge, and pH by cambridge pH meter.

This gives us great pleasure in extending our heartfelt thanks and gratitude to Prof. G. A. Edwards and Prof. J. Pandergrast of North Carolina Agricultural and Technical College for IR spectra, to Mr. N. N. Ghosh of the University College of Science, Calcutta for permitting us to work with the magnetic balance, to Prof. S. K. Siddhanta for his kindly giving us facilities and encouragement and to Mr M. Sadhu for helping us with the set up of the Duma combustion train.